

Synthesis of Mixed Ligand Complexes with Nitrido-osmium(VI) and Nitrido-osmium (VIII)

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MUCH interest has recently been shown in the chemistry of $M \equiv N$ bonded complexes of metal ions osmium¹⁻³, rhenium⁴, and molybdenum⁵. A number of mixed ligand complexes of osmium (VI) having $Os(VI) \equiv N$ group have been synthesised and characterised by elemental analysis. Presence of $Os \equiv N$ group in these compounds has been diagnosed from their spectral data in infrared region^{6,7}. Stretching frequency of the bands lies between 1020-1115 cm^{-1} depending on the nature of other ligands attached to osmium(VI) ion. Stretching frequency for $Os \equiv N$ band is given for some of the synthesised compounds in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Compound	$\nu(Os \equiv N)$ in cm^{-1}
(DipyH) $[OsNCl_4H_2O]$	1083(s)
(PhenH) $[OsNCl_4H_2O]$	1100(s)
(DipyH) $[OsNBr_4H_2O]$	1105(m)
(PhenH) $[OsNBr_4H_2O]$	1110(m)
$OsN(Oxine)_2Cl$	1110(s)
$OsNDipyBr_3$	1115(m)
$[NOsO(BigH)_2](OH)_3$	1055(m)

The compounds can be divided into two categories, one having ligand bases such as 2, 2'-dipyridyl and 1, 10-phenanthroline attached to the metal ion and the second having the protonated bases acting as cations to the complex compounds. The preparative methods have been shown schematically.

where L = 2, 2'-dipyridyl and 1, 10-phenanthroline, X = Cl, Br, and $BigH = C_2N_5H_7$.

One interesting feature of the I. R. data is, $\nu(Os \equiv N)$ of all compounds except (DipyH) $[N \equiv OsCl_4H_2O]$ and $[N \equiv Os = O(BigH)_2](OH)_3$ are very close. Very low value of $\nu(Os \equiv N)$ of $[NOs = O(BigH)_2](OH)_3$ is due to very strong donation by biguanide ligand and trans effect of $Os = O$, where the valency of Os is eight. The low value of $\nu(Os \equiv N)$ of (DipyH) $[N \equiv OsCl_4H_2O]$ is possibly due to the absence of H_2O in co-ordination sphere.

Similar compounds with rhenium(V) have been isolated. Further work is in progress for characterisation of osmium(VI) and rhenium(V) complexes.

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Organo-Cobalt(III) Complexes with Schiff Bases

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THE recent demonstration that the vitamin B₁₂ coenzyme (5'-deoxyadenosylcobalamin) contains a cobalt-carbon σ -bond^{1,2} and is a diamagnetic cobalt(III) complex containing a co-ordinated carbanion³ has stimulated research interest in the preparation and study of a wide range of organo-cobalt(III) complexes with other ligands.⁴⁻⁸ Here, in this paper, we describe the preparation and properties of some organo-cobalt(III) complexes of dibasic tetradentate Schiff bases derived by the condensation of ethylenediamine with 3-carboxysalicylaldehyde (abbreviated as BCSEN-H₄) and with orthohydroxyacetophenone (abbreviated as BHAH-H₂). This work is an extension of our previous investigations on the mixed-ligand chelates of trivalent transition metals involving Schiff bases and their organo-derivatives.⁹⁻¹⁴

Experimental :

Solvents and chemicals were purified and dried by standard methods. The electronic absorption spectra and magnetic susceptibilities were measured and elemental analysis of metal and nitrogen were performed as described previously⁹. Infrared spectra were measured and microanalysis of C, H and N were performed through commercial service of C.D.R.I., Lucknow.

Preparation of the organo-cobalt(III) complexes of bases :

(Preparations were done in N₂ atmosphere)

$[CH_3Co(BCSEN-H_2)H_2O]$, (I) :

$[Co(BCSEN-H_2)(NH_3)_2]Cl \cdot 2H_2O$ (10 m mole) was taken in 50 ml of anhydrous THF and treated dropwise under stirring at $-20^\circ C$ with Grignard reagent (30 m mole) prepared from CH_3Br and Mg in THF. The temperature was allowed to raise under stirring and after 5 hours the reaction mixture was poured in ice-cold water and neutralised with 2N HCl.

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THF was removed by distillation under vacuum and the solid obtained was then filtered, washed with water and finally recrystallised from aqueous-ethanol as red yellow crystals. Yield ~65%, m. p. decomposed above 180°.

The compound is moderately soluble in ethanol, methanol and soluble in coordinating solvents, but insoluble in water, benzene and ether. The compound is diamagnetic.

[CH₃Co(BCSEN-H₂)NH₃], (II) :

Obtained as orange-yellow crystals by bubbling ammonia gas through the suspension of [CH₃Co(BCSEN-H₂)(H₂O)], (I) in methyl alcohol for about 4 hr at 0°. Washed with petroleum ether (b. p. 40°-60°) and dried in a CaCl₂ desiccator. The compound is diamagnetic.

[CH₃Co(BCSEN-H₂)py], (III) :

Obtained by dissolving aquo-derivative (I) in pyridine, after adding light petroleum ether. The reddish yellow crystals were dried under vacuum at room temperature. The compound is diamagnetic.

[C₆H₅Co(BCSEN-H₂)H₂O], (IV) :

Obtained as reddish-yellow crystals by a method similar to (I) and using C₆H₅MgBr. Yield ~48%, m. p. 190° (dec.). The compound is diamagnetic.

[C₆H₅Co(BCSEN-H₂)(NH₃)], (V) :

This orange-red crystalline compound was prepared by bubbling ammonia gas into a solution of (IV) in NN'-dimethyl-formamide; washed with ether and dried in open air at room temperature. Yield 60%, m. p. 210 (dec.). The compound is diamagnetic.

[C₆H₅Co(BCSEN-H₂)py], (VI) :

Obtained as yellow crystals on recrystallizing (IV) from ethanol-pyridine (1 : 1) mixture; washed with petroleum ether and dried under vacuum. The compound is diamagnetic.

[C₆H₅CH₂Co(BCSEN-H₂)H₂O], (VII) :

Using C₆H₅CH₂MgBr and following the method described for (I) gave this complex as red crystals. Yield ~55%, m. p. 215° (dec.). The compound is diamagnetic.

[C₆H₅CH₂Co(BCSEN-H₂)NH₃], (VIII) :

Aquo derivative (VII) gave this compound as orange red crystals by the method described for (II) Yield ~60%, m. p. 198° (dec.). The compound is diamagnetic.

[C₆H₅CH₂Co(BCSEN-H₂)py], (IX) :

Recrystallisation of (VII) from pyridinemethanol (1 : 2) gave this yellow-brown compound. Yield 70%, m. p. 200° (dec.). The compound is diamagnetic.

[CH₃Co(BHAE)H₂O] (X) :

A suspension of Co¹¹ (BHAE) (2.10 g., 6.00 m mole) in anhydrous THF was reduced with 1% Na(Hg) under nitrogen. The green solution was separated from the amalgam and treated with CH₃I at -20°. This reaction mixture gave red orange crystalline product on treatment with water and removing THF under vacuum. The compound was recrystallised from methanol. The compound is diamagnetic.

[CH₃Co(BHAE)NH₃], (XI) :

This red compound was obtained by passing NH₃ gas through the solution of (X) in methanol. The compound is diamagnetic.

[CH₃Co(BHAE)py], (XII) :

Recrystallisation of (X) from pyridinehexane mixture gave this red-brown compound. The compound is diamagnetic.

Results and Discussion :

The organo-derivatives isolated in the present study along with their elemental analyses are set out in Table 1, while Table 2 includes the electronic absorption spectra of some representative complexes.

Treatment of [Co(BCSEN-H₂)(NH₃)₂] Cl. 2H₂O^{15,16} with appropriate Grignard reagent in THF gave the complexes [R Co(BCSEN-H₂)(H₂O)] [R=CH₃(I), C₆H₅(IV), C₆H₅CH₂(VII)] as stable red or red-yellow crystalline compounds. The water molecule from (I) can be removed on keeping the sample in a vacume desiccator over P₂O₅ at room temperature to give a green complex [CH₃Co(BCSEN-H₂)]. When the phenyl derivative (IV) and benzyl derivative (VII) are heated just under their m. p. they give green solid, (which may be considered as C₆H₅Co(BCSEN-H₂) and C₆H₅CH₂Co(BCSEN-H₂) although the pure anhydrous compounds could not be isolated by us yet. However, successful isolation of pentacoordinated R Co(BAEN) from R Co(BAEN)H₂O by heat treatment (50°-100°) is reported recently¹⁵. The presence of free-COOH group might create further complexities in our systems.

The i. r. spectra could not help us to say the nature of water molecule is complexes (I), (IV) and (VII) as the ligand contained free carboxylic group. However, the easy removal of H₂O from (I) suggests the presence of non-coordinating or loosely bound H₂O molecule in these chelates. It has been reported^{15,16} that in CH₃Co(BSEN)H₂O or in CH₃Co(BSEN)H₂O the water molecule is not coordinated with the cobalt ion. (i. r. spectral study).

By treatment of (I), (IV) and (VII) with appropriate base, the complexes [R Co(BCSEN-H₂)L] (L=NH₃ and py) are obtained (Table 1).

Reduction (in THF) of Co^{II}(BHAE) with 1% Na/Hg under N₂ produced a green solution (presumably Co^I compound, a powerful nucleophile), which on treatment with CH₃I, yielded red orange crystalline CH₃Co(BHAE)H₂O, (X). The solution of (X) in non-coordinating solvents is green in colour, presumably due to the presence of pentacoordinate species, CH₃Co(BHAE) (see later discussion).

Treatment of (X) with ammonia and pyridine yielded CH₃Co(BHAE)NH₃(XI) and CH₃Co(BHAE)py(XII) respectively.

The compounds are hydrolyzed with aqueous mineral acids, and this is remarkably accelerated by the light. (We are interested to study, this aspect of our observation in detail). This "photolability" represents connection between the present complexes and that of the corrinoids.^{17,18}

TABLE 1—ELEMENTAL ANALYSES OF ORGANO-DERIVATIVES OF SOME COBALT(III) COMPLEXES OF SCHIFF BASES

Sl. No.	Complex	Found %				Calc. %			
		C	H	N	Co	C	H	N	Co
I.	[CH ₃ Co(BCSEN-H ₂)H ₂ O]	51.44	4.52	6.78	13.48	51.12	4.26	6.27	13.23
II.	[CH ₃ Co(BCSEN-H ₂)NH ₃]	51.80	5.01	9.50	13.42	51.23	4.49	9.43	13.26
III.	[CH ₃ Co(BCSEN-H ₂)py] ^a	56.92	4.76	8.39	12.00	56.80	4.33	8.28	11.63
IV.	[C ₆ H ₅ Co(BCSEN-H ₂)H ₂ O]	57.01	4.33	5.85	11.02	56.69	4.13	5.51	11.61
V.	[C ₆ H ₅ Co(BCSEN-H ₂)NH ₃]	55.98	4.21	7.99	12.00	56.80	4.34	8.24	11.63
VI.	[C ₆ H ₅ Co(BCSEN-H ₂)py]	61.24	4.40	7.58	10.78	61.16	4.22	7.38	10.37
VII.	[C ₆ H ₅ Co(BCSEN-H ₂)H ₂ O]	60.00	4.58	5.88	11.38	59.46	4.40	5.30	11.32
VIII.	[C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ Co(BCSEN-H ₂)NH ₃]	57.28	5.00	8.22	11.42	57.58	4.60	8.06	11.32
IX.	[C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ Co(BCSEN-H ₂)py]	62.02	4.58	7.28	10.24	61.75	4.40	7.20	10.12
X.	[CH ₃ Co(BHAE)H ₂ O]	58.98	6.23	7.45	15.49	59.06	5.95	7.25	15.29
XI.	[CH ₃ Co(BHAE)NH ₃]	59.48	6.33	11.23	15.30	59.21	6.23	10.91	15.32
XII.	[CH ₃ Co(BHAE)py]	64.02	6.00	9.48	13.42	64.43	5.81	9.39	13.20

a) py=pyridine

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC SPECTRA OF SOME ORGANO-DERIVATIVES OF COBALT(III) COMPLEXES OF SCHIFF BASE

Complex	Frequencies (cm ⁻¹ × 10 ⁻³) and log ε _{max} (in brackets) ^a	Solvent
[CH ₃ Co(BCSEN-H ₂)H ₂ O], (I)	29.58(4.00); 24.92(3.7); 21.8(sh); 15.81(sh)	CH ₂ Cl ₂ /EtOH
[CH ₃ Co(BCSEN-H ₂)], (III)	29.08(3.81); 25.00(sh); 22.61(sh); 20.4(sh)	C ₆ H ₅ N/EtOH
[C ₆ H ₅ Co(BCSEN-H ₂)H ₂ O] ^b , (IV)	29.00; 25.92(sh); 22.1(sh); 15.8(sh)	CH ₂ Cl ₂ /EtOH
[C ₆ H ₅ Co(BCSEN-H ₂)py], (VI)	28.48(3.48); 23.8(sh); 21.00(sh)	C ₆ H ₅ N/EtOH
[CH ₃ Co(BHAE)H ₂ O] (X)	25.00(sh); 20.18(sh); 15.80(2.8)	CHCl ₃
[CH ₃ Co(BHAE)py], (XII)	26.00(3.92); 18.00(sh); 14.11(sh)	C ₆ H ₅ N/EtOH

a) log ε_{max} values are approximate in many cases due to solubility limitations.

b) spectrum of a saturated solution was taken; intensities were not calculated.

Reaction of KCN with CH₃Co(BCSEN-H₂)H₂O in aqueous-ethanol (under reflux) leads to the cleavage of cobalt-carbon bond and substitution of H₂O ligand yielding K[Co(BCSEN-H₂)(CN)₂], which was identified through elemental analyses, and i. r. spectra.

The above results reveal the similarity between the course of the reaction of hexacoordinated chelate complexes of Co(III) with BSEN¹⁶ (NN'-ethylene bis(salicylideneiminato) dianion), BAEN¹⁵ (=NN'-ethylene bis(acetylacetoniminato)dianion) and BCSEN-H₂ with Grignard reagents in THF.

The compounds, reported in this study, are sufficiently stable at room temperatures and in atmospheric conditions. The diamagnetic nature of these compounds demonstrates the presence of trivalent cobalt. The present organo-derivatives of cobalt(III) contain the dianion of the tetradentate Schiff base in the x-y plane, the alkyl (or aryl) group and a sixth ligand (whenever present) on the z-axis in the trans position. The carbanions here function as a ligand as found in the alkyl cobalamines³.

Electronic absorption spectra in solution of some representative compounds are recorded in Table 2. The complexes (I), (IV) and (X) in non-coordinating solvents show bands around 15,800 cm⁻¹, which may be taken as a proof of the presence of pentacoordinated species in solutions. This band displaced to about 20,000 cm⁻¹ in the hexacoordinated species (e. g. [R Co(BCSEN-H₂)py], see Table I and Table 2). However, the later band may be mixed up with transitions of other origin.^{12,13} This is a tentative interpretation of the spectral bands, observed in the present study.

The occurrence of four bands (sufficiently strong) between 30,000 and 15,000 cm⁻¹ in the present complexes could be explained by very low symmetry of the molecules and by vibronic coupling. The mixing of metal and ligand orbitals are important in the systems under study.¹⁹

The stabilization of cobalt carbon bond results¹⁶ from the proper stereochemical arrangement of the tetradentate ligand (approximately in the x-y plane) and participation of electrons of the cobalt atom in the orbitals of the conjugate systems of chelate rings (metal-ligand donor π bonds). The electrons of the conjugate systems of ligands interacts more strongly with p_x, d_{xy} and d_{yz} electrons of the metal giving π-molecular orbitals while the d_{x²-y²}, d_{xy} and d_{x²-y²}-2 electrons are mainly involved in the metal to ligand σ-bonds in the x-y plane.²⁰}}

As a consequence of the above interactions, the energy and overlapping of the appropriate orbitals of the metal on the z-axis are properly adjusted to give stable σ-bonding molecular orbitals, with alkyl or aryl groups. The existence of stable, apparently pentacoordinated species [R Co (BAEN)]¹⁵ and [R Co (BSEN)]¹⁶ suggests that the influence of the sixth ligand on the z-axis is not essential in the stabilization of the cobalt-carbon bond.

Recently it has been argued that the transition metal to carbon bond is no weaker than the bonds between carbon and other metallic elements and that the main purpose of additional ligands is stabilizing compounds with metal to carbon σ-bonds in merely the blocking of the coordination sites required for decomposition reactions to proceed.^{21,22}

NOTES

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